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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL AZEEZ bearing USN 6SU20ML001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AFRA SULTHANA A bearing USN 6SU20ML002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AHAMMED HAAFIZ M bearing USN 6SU20ML003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISATH SANIYA bearing USN 6SU20ML004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKBAR SIDDIQ bearing USN 6SU20ML005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHILA VIJAYAKUMAR bearing USN 6SU20ML006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALTHAF MAHAMOOD** bearing USN **6SU20ML007** has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMAYA T P bearing USN 6SU20ML008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJU MOHANAN bearing USN 6SU20ML009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE A bearing USN 6SU20ML010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DILNA E bearing USN 6SU20ML011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DIYA P S bearing USN 6SU20ML012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAYIS ABDUL LATHEEF bearing USN 6SU20ML013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FEBIN SUNNY bearing USN 6SU20ML014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNAN T J** bearing USN **6SU20ML015** has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HAYA ROOSH MEHAR M bearing USN 6SU20ML016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JEBIN BAJI bearing USN 6SU20ML017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SAHLE PEEDIKAYIL bearing USN 6SU20ML018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA DIVAKAR bearing USN 6SU20ML019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDHANA P bearing USN 6SU20ML020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAYUJYA A P bearing USN 6SU20ML021 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHEIK MUHAMMED RIYAF bearing USN 6SU20ML022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIVAKUMAR B L** bearing USN **6SU20ML023** has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWETHA GANGAN C bearing USN 6SU20ML024 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZIFA KHAN bearing USN 6SU20ML025 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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